

D4.4 CHALLENGE TEST FOR DEMONSTRATION OF CLEANING PROCESSES WORK PACKAGE 4

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cleaning efficiency

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CONTENTS

Contents	3
List of figures	3
List of tables.....	3
Publishable executive summary.....	4
Abbreviations	5
1. Introduction	6
2. Challenge tests for demonstrating cleaning efficiency	7
a. Background.....	7
b. Procedure and Methods	8
c. Results	10
3. Discussion	13

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1: The two recycling pathways subject to the performed challenge tests.	7
Figure 2: The flakes that were contaminated for the experiments (left) and the barrels for the contamination procedure (right).....	9
Figure 3: GC-FID chromatogram of a dichloromethane extract for one of the spiked samples. 11	11

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1: Model contaminants used for the challenge test with details of their molecular weight, functional groups and physical properties.....	8
Table 2: Samples for “Deinking – Mechanical Recycling – Deodorisation” Cascade	9
Table 3: Samples for Solvent-based Recycling	9
Table 4: Detection limits of the applied method for the surrogates (Solvent-based recycling process).....	10
Table 5: Calculated cleaning efficiencies in % per substance for the “Deinking – Mechanical Recycling – Deodorisation” Cascade.....	12
Table 6: Calculated cleaning efficiencies in % per substance for the Solvent-based recycling process.....	12
Table 7: Concentrations of the model contaminants in the material (mean values and standard deviation); „Deinking – Mechanical Recycling – Deodorisation” Cascade.....	16
Table 8: Concentrations of the model contaminants in the material (mean values and standard deviation); Solvent-based recycling process.....	17

PUBLISHABLE EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The aim of the performed challenge test study was to determine if the envisaged recycling technologies and cascades are capable of efficiently removing contaminants. To date, recycling of post-consumer plastics was mainly centered on PET-material. Within this project, the PCR material that was part of the final laminate structure was LDPE.

As a current approach already well-established for PET-material, challenge tests are performed to determine the cleaning efficiency of recycling processes. These tests involve the intentional spiking of the input material with high concentrations of surrogate compounds that simulate typical contaminants with a wide range of physico-chemical properties. This intentional contamination is followed by the subsequent analysis of the residual content of these surrogates after the respective recycling treatments (i.e. decontamination steps). Consequently, the outcome of these challenge tests will allow to conclude on the cleaning efficiency of the recycling treatments. The established cleaning efficiencies is one essential decision criterion to assess recyclates' qualities and their suitability to be re-used in food packaging and home/personal care applications.

The investigated solvent-based recycling techniques showed good cleaning efficiencies ranging from at least 89 – 98 % for the investigated surrogates up to a molecular weight of 390 g/mol. However, calculation of the assigned cleaning efficiencies was limited by the LOQ of the applied analytical method, so that the actual cleaning efficiencies could be even higher than currently demonstrated.

For the investigated cascade consisting of a sequence of “water-based deinking, densification, granulation and deodorization” step, the achieved overall cleaning efficiency of the cascade ranged from 81 – 98 % for the investigated surrogates up to a molecular weight of 390 g/mol.

Due to the sorption and diffusion properties of polyolefins additional surrogates with a molecular weight of 1000 g/mol should be included as an adaptation step of the challenge test setup to further “challenge” this decontamination technology with regard to those higher molecular weight (non-volatile) surrogates. Such substances >700 g/mol must be analysed using HPLC as a complementary analytical technique to the here used gas chromatographic analyses.

In addition, it was shown that the flake matrix as used for the initial contamination led to an uneven distribution of the surrogates in the material, which resulted in high standard deviations. For future challenge tests on film flakes, an adaption of the contamination process should be considered.

ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	
C_{p0}	Initial concentration
EFSA	European Food Safety Authority
DEHA	Diethylhexyl adipate
GC-FID	Gas chromatograph - Flame Ionization Detector
HPLC	High performance liquid chromatography
LDPE	Low density polyethylene
LOQ	Limit of quantification
M_w	Molecular weight
PCR	Post-consumer recyclates
PET	Polyethylene terephthalate
ppm	Part per million
SOA	state-of-the-art
TEHTM or TOTM	Tris(ethylhexyl) trimellitate
WP	Work package

1. INTRODUCTION

The main objective of work package (WP) 4 was to define, evaluate and assess innovative recycling strategies and newly developed packaging structures for the use of recycled polyethylene in flexible packaging for food and personal care applications.

For this purpose, analytical migration and compliance testing was applied in order to assess and ensure food regulatory compliance of the laminate structures developed within this project.

Task 4.3 aimed to establish the cleaning efficiency of the recycling processes within the project for the production of PCR material, including the delamination/deinking processes and the solvent-based recycling process, by using so-called “challenge tests”.

For the challenge test, the input material was intentionally contaminated with a defined set of substances (surrogates) with different chemical/physical properties and molecular weight followed by the subsequent analysis of the residual content of these surrogates after the respective recycling treatments (i.e. decontamination steps). Consequently, the outcome of these challenge tests allowed to conclude on the cleaning efficiency of the recycling treatments. The established cleaning efficiencies is one essential decision criterion to assess recyclates' qualities and their suitability to be re-used in food packaging and home/personal care applications.

2. CHALLENGE TESTS FOR DEMONSTRATING CLEANING EFFICIENCY

a. Background

Challenge tests are an already well-established quality control tool for recycling processes of PET materials by using artificial contaminants and by comparing the levels of contamination in the output material vs. the input material.

These challenge tests are based on the following procedure:

Organic compounds ("model contaminants" or "surrogates") are spiked onto the input material. These surrogates are substances with different physico-chemical characteristics and are representatives of possible chemical classes of contaminants. Normally, the surrogates are added to the input material at exaggerated concentrations. The initial concentration (c_{p0} ; in the input material after spiking) and their concentration after passing through the different steps of the recycling treatment is determined by analytical measurements. This allows to calculate the decontamination/cleaning efficiency, which is expressed as percentage of reduction of the surrogate levels compared to the initial concentration before entering the recycling process¹.

For the challenge test experiments performed within the project, the set of surrogates as given in Table 1 was used. The tests were performed on the input flexible packaging material² of Loop 2 and for the following cascades:

1) "Solvent-based Recycling"

2) "Water-based Deinking – Mechanical Recycling – Deodorisation" Cascade

Figure 1: The two recycling pathways subject to the performed challenge tests.

¹ EFSA Panel on food contact materials, enzymes, flavourings and processing aids (CEF); Scientific Opinion on the criteria to be used for safety evaluation of a mechanical recycling process to produce recycled PET intended to be used for manufacture of materials and articles in contact with food. EFSA Journal 2011;9(7):2184. [25 pp.] doi:10.2903/j.efsa.2011.2184.

² The structure of the Loop2 flexible packaging material used here is described in Deliverable D6.3 (Chapter 2) in detail.

³ Hydrodyn was the sub-contractor of UGENT to perform at scale the developed water-based deinking processes.

Table 1: Model contaminants used for the challenge test with details of their molecular weight, functional groups and physical properties

Substance	M _w ^[a]	Functional groups	Properties
Toluene	92.1	Aromatic hydrocarbon	volatile, non-polar
Chlorobenzene	112.6	Aromatic hydrocarbon, halogen-containing	volatile, polar
Limonene	136.2	Aliphatic hydrocarbon	volatile, non-polar
Phenylcyclohexane	160.3	Aromatic hydrocarbon	low volatility, non-polar
Benzophenone	182.2	Aromatic ketone	low volatility, polar
Butyl salicylate	194.2	Aliphatic ester	non-volatile, non-polar
Methyl palmitate	270.5	Aliphatic ester	non-volatile, medium-polar
Diethylhexyl adipate (DEHA)	390.6	Aliphatic ester	non-volatile, medium-polar
Tris(ethylhexyl) trimellitate (TEHTM; TOTM)	546.8	Aromatic ester	non-volatile, medium-polar

^[a]Molecular weight (M_w) in g mol⁻¹

b. Procedure and Methods

Contamination and sample shipment

The input material for the challenge tests were shredded flakes (40 mm) of Loop 2 film material.

56 kg of shredded LDPE film (flakes) were contaminated according to the following procedure at Fraunhofer IVV: The 56 kg of shredded flakes were filled into 8 barrels (7 kg each). To each of the barrels, a mixture of 7 ml toluene, 7 ml chlorobenzene, 7 ml limonene, 7 ml phenyl cyclohexane, 7 g benzophenone, 7 ml butyl salicylate, 7 g methyl palmitate, 7 g diethylhexyl adipate and 7 g tris(ethylhexyl) trimellitate was given (contamination levels: approx. 1000 ppm). Subsequently the barrels were sealed and stored for 7 d at 50 °C. The sealed barrels were turned/rolled each day. Subsequently, the flakes were combined into 2 barrels. Samples were drawn in order to determine the initial surrogates' concentration c_{p_0} according to the extraction and analysis methods as given below. The samples were then shipped to the project partners following the above described cascade and additionally applying solvent-based recycling (Figure 1). After each essential process step, samples were drawn, sent back to Fraunhofer IVV and analysed for the residual content of the surrogates. Based on these residual concentrations in relation to the initial concentration before entering the recycling process (c_{p_0}), the cleaning efficiencies can be calculated stepwise up to the overall process.

The sample overview is given in Table 2 and Table 3.

Figure 2: The flakes that were contaminated for the experiments (left) and the barrels for the contamination procedure (right)

Table 2: Samples for “Water-based Deinking – Mechanical Recycling – Deodorisation” Cascade

Sample No	Description	Replicates for analysis
1	Contaminated flakes before entering the process (C_{p_0} analysis)	28
2	Pre-Washing at Hydrodyn (Step 1) incl. drying; flakes	4
3	Hot-Washing at Hydrodyn (Step 2) incl. drying; flakes	4
4	Rinsing at Hydrodyn (Step 3) incl. drying; flakes	4
5	Before densification (after arrival) at Suez; flakes	4
6	After densification at Suez; flakes	4
7	After granulation at Suez; granulate	4
8	After deodorisation at Kreyenborg; granulate	4

Table 3: Samples for Solvent-based Recycling

Sample No	Description	Replicates for analysis
1	Contaminated flakes before entering the process (C_{p_0} analysis)	8
23 a	Granulate after state-of-the-art (SOA) solvent-based recycling process, #Batch 1	2
23 b	Granulate after state-of-the-art (SOA) solvent-based recycling process, #Batch 2	2
23 c	Granulate after solvent-based recycling with additional purification unit “Purification 2”, #Batch 3	2

Extraction method and analytical method

In each case a 1.0 g sample was weighed into a headspace-vial and extracted twice with 10 ml dichloromethane for 3 d at 40 °C (duplicate experiment). The extracts were then analyzed by gas chromatography coupled to flame ionization detection (FID). The FID signals of the model contaminants in the gas chromatogram were integrated. The concentrations of the respective contaminants were determined from calibration graphs obtained using external standards.

Table 4: Limits of quantifications of the applied method for the surrogates (“Water-based Deinking – Mechanical Recycling – Deodorisation” Cascade)

Surrogate	Limit of quantification - LOQ [µg/g material]*
Toluene	13
Chlorobenzene	25
Limonene	21
Phenyl cyclohexane	58
Butyl salicylate	220
Benzophenone	107
Methyl palmitate	101
Diethylhexyladipate DEHA	61
Tris(ethylhexyl)trimellitate TEHTM, TOTM	61

Table 5: Limits of quantification of the applied method for the surrogates (Solvent-based recycling process)

Surrogate	Limit of quantification - LOQ [µg/g material]*
Toluene	13
Chlorobenzene	25
Limonene	21
Phenyl cyclohexane	58
Butyl salicylate	110
Benzophenone	107
Methyl palmitate	51
Diethylhexyladipate DEHA	61
Tris(ethylhexyl)trimellitate TEHTM, TOTM	61

*: It has to be noted that the LOQs given in the tables above correspond to LOQs of standard substances in the pure solvent that were recalculated to the extraction ratio of 1 g / 10 ml.

c. Results

The obtained chromatograms of the spiked samples showed that two of the surrogate substances could not be evaluated quantitatively due to coelution:

- Tris(ethylhexyl)trimellitate coeluted with the antioxidant Irgafos® 168 (Tris(2,4-di-tert-butylphenyl)phosphite) present in the sample material
- Butyl salicylate coeluted with an internal standard that was added to the sample extracts

Figure 3: GC-FID chromatogram of a dichloromethane extract for one of the spiked samples. The surrogate Tris(ethylhexyl)trimellitate (TOTM) coelutes with the antioxidant Irgafos® 168

Consequently, tris(ethylhexyl)trimellitate and butyl salicylate were not used to evaluate cleaning efficiencies.

Furthermore, it was also observed that particularly the contaminated input samples (sample 1) showed high standard deviations in the quantification results, most possibly as a result of the flake structure of the input material.

The following tables present the cleaning efficiencies in % per substance for the two investigated recycling pathways (“Water-based Deinking – Mechanical Recycling – Deodorisation” Cascade and “Solvent-based recycling process”). The concentrations and standard deviations for the input samples are given in the ANNEX. For quantification values at or below the LOQs, the calculation was performed with the respective LOQ. The values were not corrected for blank values (worst case).

Table 6: Calculated cleaning efficiencies in % per substance for the “Water-based Deinking – Mechanical Recycling – Deodorisation” Cascade

Sample / Step	Toluene	Chloro-benzene	Limonene	Phenyl cyclohexane	Benzo-phenone	Methyl palmitate	DEHA
2 / Pre-Washing	61	60	45	40	35	38	(63)
3 / Hot-Washing	97	96	65	54	65	90	(81)
4 / Rinsing	≥ 98	≥ 97	82	69	82	88	(79)
5 / Before dens.	≥ 98	≥ 97	79	63	74	90	(76)
6 / Densification	≥ 98	≥ 97	90	72	76	89	(81)
7 / Granulation	≥ 98	≥ 97	91	76	76	82	(81)
8 / Deodorization	≥ 98	≥ 97	≥ 98	≥ 95	≥ 93	87	(81)

Annotation: the determined values were characterized by high standard deviations for the reference sample 1; in particular for DEHA, which indicates an inhomogeneous distribution in the material (see ANNEX).

Table 7: Calculated cleaning efficiencies in % per substance for the solvent-based recycling process

Sample / Step	Toluene	Chloro-benzene	Limonene	Phenyl cyclohexane	Benzo-phenone	Methyl palmitate	DEHA
23 a / SOA, #1	≥ 97	≥ 97	≥ 98	≥ 94	≥ 89	≥ 94	≥ (92)
23 b / SOA, #2	≥ 97	≥ 97	≥ 98	≥ 94	≥ 89	≥ 94	≥ (91)
23 c / Additional purification, #3	≥ 97	≥ 97	≥ 98	≥ 94	≥ 89	≥ 94	≥ (91)

Annotation: the determined values were characterized by high standard deviations for the reference sample 1; in particular for DEHA, which indicates an inhomogeneous distribution in the material (see ANNEX).

3. DISCUSSION

The aim of the performed study was to determine if the envisaged recycling technologies and cascades are capable of efficiently removing contaminants. To date, recycling of post-consumer plastics was mainly centered on PET-material. Within this project, the PCR material that will be part of the final laminate structure is LDPE.

As a current approach already well-established for PET-material, challenge tests are performed to determine the cleaning efficiency of recycling processes. These tests involve spiking the input material with high concentrations of surrogate compounds that simulate contaminants with a wide range of physico-chemical properties.

For PET-material, the molecular weight of surrogates selected for challenge tests is usually only up to approx. 300 g/mol. Due to the sorption and diffusion properties of polyolefins, a wider molecular weight range should be considered⁴. Therefore, two substances with a higher molecular weight (DEHA and TEHTM) were included as a first adoption step (see Table 1).

From the cleaning efficiencies determined for the two investigated recycling pathways (see Table 6 and Table 7), the following conclusions can be drawn:

“Water-based Deinking – Mechanical Recycling – Deodorisation” Cascade

- the decontamination efficiency is the highest for the substances with the lowest molecular weight (toluene, chlorobenzene and limonene). The cleaning efficiencies for the surrogates with higher molecular weight was basically lower.
- with the washing steps (marking the first step of a recycling treatment) the contaminants could only be removed partially. Based on the obtained values, the hot-washing was more effective than the pre-washing.
- the final deodorization step showed high decontamination efficiencies for the investigated volatile substances.
- it was also observed that particularly the contaminated input samples (sample 1) showed high standard deviations in the quantification results, which indicates an inhomogeneous distribution of the analytes and is most possibly as a result of the flake structure of the input material. (The material that was contaminated were shredded film flakes (LDPE)).

Solvent-based recycling

- The residual levels of the employed surrogates were at / below the LOQ of the used analytical GC method. Therefore, calculation of the assigned cleaning efficiencies was limited by the LOQ so that the actual cleaning efficiencies could be even higher than currently demonstrated.

⁴ Stella Palkopoulou, Catherine Joly, Alexandre Feigenbaum, Constantine D. Papaspyrides, Patrice Dole, Critical review on challenge tests to demonstrate decontamination of polyolefins intended for food contact applications, Trends in Food Science & Technology, Volume 49, 2016, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tifs.2015.12.003>.

- However, a clear reduction of the surrogates could already be shown: High cleaning efficiencies of up to 98 % were achieved for the state-of-the-art solvent-based recycling process (indicative demonstration).
- In general, the solvent-based recycling seemed to be more efficient in the removal of surrogates of higher molecular weight (e.g. DEHA).
- Due to the currently established LOQ, it was not possible to conclude on the efficiency of the additional purification unit used in the solvent-based recycling process.

4. SUMMARY AND OUTLOOK

The investigated solvent-based recycling techniques showed good cleaning efficiencies ranging from at least 89 – 98 % for the investigated surrogates up to a molecular weight of 390 g/mol. However, calculation of the assigned cleaning efficiencies was limited by the LOQ of the applied analytical method, so that the actual cleaning efficiencies could be even higher than currently demonstrated.

For the investigated cascade consisting of a sequence of “water-based deinking, densification, granulation and deodorization” step, the achieved overall cleaning efficiency of the cascade ranged from 81 – 98 % for the investigated surrogates up to a molecular weight of 390 g/mol.

For both investigated decontamination pathways, the cleaning efficiencies for the larger molecules (like DEHA) were lower than for small volatile surrogates such as toluene and limonene. Due to the sorption and diffusion properties of polyolefins⁴, it can be expected that for other, in particular, non-volatile surrogates with even higher molecular weight (up to 1000 g/mol) the cleaning efficiencies will be even lower and are difficult to remove with currently established mechanical recycling technologies^{5,6}.

Due to the sorption and diffusion properties of polyolefins additional surrogates with a molecular weight of up to 1000 g/mol should be included for a comprehensive assessment of the decontamination capabilities of decontamination technologies for polyolefins. Consequently, an adaptation step of the challenge test setup is required to further “challenge” the decontamination technologies regarding those higher molecular weight (non-volatile) surrogates. Such substances >700 g/mol must be analysed using HPLC as a complementary analytical technique.

In addition to the adoption of the challenge test design with regard to the surrogates, the analytical methods need to be optimized, e.g. to avoid co-elution and to obtain lower LOQs, in order to achieve a “standard procedure for polyolefins”.

Within the project the contamination of LDPE-based flakes was performed for the very first time based on the experience of already established challenge test design for PET. Regarding the technical realization of the contamination process, it was recognizable that the contamination

⁵ EFSA Scientific Opinion on the safety assessment of the processes ‘Biffa Polymers’ and ‘CLRrHDPE’ used to recycle high-density polyethylene bottles for use as food contact material. EFSA Journal 2015, 13(2), 4016; <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2015.4016>

⁶ EFSA Safety assessment of the process Starlinger recoSTAR HDPE FC 1 – PET2PET used to recycle post-consumer HDPE closures into food contact closures. EFSA Journal 2022, 20(1), 7001; <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2022.7001>

of shredded flakes introduced some difficulties. Typically granulates (like in the PET super-clean processes) are being used. High standard deviations of the determined initial concentration (C_{PO}) showed that the surrogates (in particular the larger molecules) were not evenly distributed in the film flake matrix, but that some agglomerations of highly contaminated flakes (“hot spots”) must have existed in the barrels. For future challenge tests, when using film flakes as input material, improved rolling / mixture process should be considered.

It should also be noted that the solvent-based pathway investigated within the project was intentionally performed at a small technical scale. We recommend that further challenge tests should also include an upscaling to pre-industrial scale as a next step.

For a final evaluation of recycled plastics, (and the potential re-use in sensitive packaging applications such as food packaging) the following aspects need to be considered in addition to the cleaning efficiency: identity and concentration of contaminants, potential transfer onto food (migration) under the foreseen conditions of use and consumers’ exposure scenarios. These aspects are discussed in complementary tasks of WP 4.

ANNEX

NOTE: All given concentrations were not corrected for the corresponding blank values. A standard deviation is given for the input sample 1. Number of investigated replicates: see Table 2 and Table 3.

Table 8: Concentrations of the model contaminants in the material (mean values and standard deviation for sample 1); „Water-based Deinking – Mechanical Recycling – Deodorisation“ Cascade

Sample	Concentration [mg/kg, ppm]						
	Toluene	Chloro-benzene	Limonene	Phenyl cyclohexane	Benzophenone	Methyl palmitate	DEHA
Sample 1 (cp)	521 ± 52	945 ± 56	1054 ± 108	1191 ± 123	1502 ± 157	1132 ± 251	1198 ± 617
Sample 2	201	380	585	717	981	699	439
Sample 3	17	41	371	549	522	119	223
Sample 4	≤ 13*	≤ 25*	189	368	277	133	247
Sample 5	≤ 13*	≤ 25*	218	441	396	117	290
Sample 6	≤ 13*	≤ 25*	113	339	366	123	233
Sample 7	≤ 13*	≤ 25*	94	285	356	199	224
Sample 8	≤ 13*	≤ 25*	≤ 21*	≤ 58*	≤ 107*	150	226

*corresponding to the LOQ (see Table 4)

Table 9: Concentrations of the model contaminants in the material (mean values and standard deviation for sample 1); Solvent-based recycling process

Sample	Concentration [mg/kg, ppm]						
	Toluene	Chloro-benzene	Limonene	Phenyl cyclohexane	Benzophenone	Methyl palmitate	DEHA
Sample 1 (cp₀)	472 ± 70	862 ± 6	935 ± 17	981 ± 25	991 ± 44	806 ± 48	710 ± 197
23 a	≤ 13*	≤ 25*	≤ 21*	≤ 58*	≤ 107*	≤ 51*	≤ 61*
23 b	≤ 13*	≤ 25*	≤ 21*	≤ 58*	≤ 107*	≤ 51*	64
23 c	≤ 13*	≤ 25*	≤ 21*	≤ 58*	≤ 107*	≤ 51*	≤ 61*

*corresponding to the LOQ (see Table 5)

